

III Annual Italian Reproducibility Network Meeting L'Open Science in Italia

VENERDÌ 23 FEBBRAIO 2024

“Open science research practices”
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Title: Replicability and transparency in qualitative research – a case study from Cultural Heritage

Contributor(s): Bianca Gualandi, Alice Bordignon, Silvio Peroni

Affiliation(s): Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, Università di Bologna

Abstract:

Although Arts and Humanities have not been swept by the “reproducibility crisis” as other disciplines have, reproducibility is a key concern for anybody doing research. When working with qualitative data, however, we usually talk about replicability, or the ability to arrive at the same findings by collecting new data, possibly with different methodologies¹. We present as case study the digital twin of the temporary exhibition “The Other Renaissance”², currently under development within the PNRR Project CHANGES - Spoke 4. The original exhibition consisted of a collection of more than 200 objects, mostly belonging to the naturalist Ulisse Aldrovandi and never exhibited before. The acquisition process – made particularly challenging by the high number of institutions involved, the size and nature of the objects, and the original exhibition setup – was preceded and aided by the establishment of shared workflows, with the real-time and simultaneous collection of processural metadata following a specific model. This same approach is being followed across all phases of the project: processing, modelling, optimization, export of the data and metadata in specific formats and upload of the 3D models to a web-based framework. Saving data and metadata in shared spaces provided transparency of processes and results and allowed for peer-review within the group. In hermeneutical fields, where multiple interpretations can coexist and the researchers’ methodological background play a central role, Open Science takes the form of transparency, through careful documentation of the research process, to test the robustness of the approach and allow for replication.

¹ <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/reproducible-research/overview/overview-definitions>

² <https://site.unibo.it/aldrovandi500/en/mostra-l-altro-rinascimento>

Title: The first steps of the Italian Community of Data Stewards.

Contributor(s): Giulia Caldoni¹, Valentina Pasquale², Emma Lazzeri³, Sara Di Giorgio³, Chiara Basalti¹, Monica Forni¹

Affiliation(s):¹ Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna;² Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia;³ GARR.

Abstract:

The EOSC guidelines for the development of Open Science within research institutions identify the need for professional figures supporting the proper management of research data, identified as ‘data stewards’. The Italian landscape presents a variety of specialists performing this role, but their position and activities often vary depending on the institution they belong to. ICDI and Skills4EOSC launched a survey in April 2023, during the Open Science Café where the University of Bologna presented its Research Data Management support services. Via this survey, a national mapping of the professionals identifying themselves as data stewards was performed and put the foundation to the Italian Community of Data Stewards. The first meeting of the community brought together more than fifty

professionals to discuss the recognition and professional growth of data stewards, which passes through the possibility of collaboration among peers. The views gathered reflect the different degrees of maturity of the data stewardship experience at the national level, providing the basis for identifying and directing the activities of the community itself.

Title: An open-access reading assessment tool: ROAR (Rapid Online Assessment of Reading) – Italian version

Contributor(s): Sendy Caffarra¹, Emanuele Casani^{1,2}, Wanjing Anya Ma³, Kyle Montville³, Jason D. Yeatman³

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Abstract:

ROAR (Rapid Online Assessment of Reading) is an open-access tool that provides an online screening battery of foundational reading skills for students from 5 to 18 years of age. It has shown high validity and reliability in American English (Gijbels et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2023; Yeatman et al., 2021), approximating in-person standardized reading tests with high accuracy ($r=0.94$). The platform is coded in Javascript and publicly stored on GitHub (<https://github.com/yeatmanlab/roar-dashboard>) to guarantee Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). It is automatically administered through a web browser without requiring the presence of a proctor (although there might be minimal assistance needed for the younger kids). After the administration, it provides a report with a set of scores, percentile scores, and risk designations, which can be used to identify children who need support.

This open-access online platform can be flexibly adapted to other languages with different orthographic transparencies compared to English to test for the generalizability of this reading assessment tool. Here we present an adaptation of this open-access online tool to the Italian language. Other in-progress adaptations include Spanish, Portuguese, German, and a Catalan version is in the pipeline. This platform will guarantee an open-access, freely available, and multilingual tool which can be accessed from different countries through a unique web app for the screening of reading difficulties in primary and secondary schools, thus adding a translational component to FAIR open-access principles.

Title: Extending BIDS to lung CT imaging: right here, right now

Contributors: Giulia Raffaella De Luca¹, Armand Violle², Stefano Diciotti^{1,3}

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Abstract:

Medical imaging heavily relies on the DICOM format, known for its complexity, vendor dependence, and privacy issues. Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) was

introduced to ensure data interoperability in neuroimaging and now supports magnetic resonance (MR), electroencephalography, and other related modalities. Extending BIDS to computed tomography (CT) could broaden the standard imaging modalities spectrum and expose it beyond neuroimaging, supporting the creation of safe, findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) datasets, an essential step to enable reproducibility and automation of healthcare tasks. To this aim, we developed a framework that adapts DICOM CT directories for the conversion to BIDS, transforms DICOM CT images to BIDS using the BIDScoin application with a custom, CT-friendly BIDSmap template, curates and pre-processes the data, extracts derived data using open-source artificial intelligence (AI) tools and stores them in a BIDS-compliant fashion. The framework demonstrated robust and seamless adaptability to various CT scanners and computational resources. The created BIDS dataset counts 7565 lung CT series of 1156 subjects from the National Lung Screening Trial. Our successful adaptation of BIDS to lung CT imaging allowed the easy deployment of AI applications for the evaluation of emphysema and the prediction of lung cancer and cardiovascular risk on the BIDS standardized dataset. This study paves the way for fostering good practice diffusion, collaboration, and research synergy beyond neuroimaging. This progress in digital medicine brings technology as a valuable tool for healthcare, ultimately improving patient outcomes and revolutionizing the medical field.

References

Gijbels et al., 2023, <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/5z2gh>

Ma et al., 2023, <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/7tpx2>

Yeatman et al., 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-85907-x>

Title: Decoding the dilemma: reproducibility pitfalls in Machine Learning with limited medical data

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Abstract:

Machine learning (ML) techniques have been increasingly adopted in Medicine and Healthcare. However, the paucity of medical data poses a challenge to reproducibility. We analyzed the variability in the performances of a deep learning model for optical computed tomography (OCT) retinal image classification. Among various reasons, this variability stems from the small training set size. Leveraging the MedMNIST dataset and a ResNet-18 network, we distinguished choroidal neovascularization from normal choroids across 88845 OCT images (88345 for the overall training set and 500 for a unique test set). We simulated small training sets by randomly extracting bootstrap sets containing {50, 100, 1000, 5000, 10000, 88345} images from the overall training set. To explore the impact of training set size on performance variability, we trained a ResNet-18 network on each training set and evaluated it on the test set, repeating this process 20 times per subset size. Our results, measured in terms of median (interquartile range) area under the Receiver Operating Characteristics curve, revealed poor performance and high variability

(indicative of poor reproducibility) for smaller training set sizes, i.e., 0.58 (0.16), 0.80 (0.10) for 50 and 100 images, respectively. In contrast, larger training set sizes exhibited improved performance and reduced variability (indicating high reproducibility), i.e., 0.89 (0.07), 0.96 (0.02), 0.95 (0.04), and 0.97 (0.02) from 1000 to 88345 images. This study underscores the potential pitfalls of ML systems trained on small medical datasets. It also highlights the risk of compromised reproducibility, questioning the reliability and real-world impact of ML systems' performance.

Title: The multiverse approach in multilab projects: we need robustness to navigate uncertainty

Contributor(s): Giulia Calignano and Psicostat Core Team

Affiliation: DPSS, UNIPD

Abstract:

What happens when many collaborators decide to consider many plausible forking paths in data analysis? The present contribution offers a brief journey through the cases of the Pupil Collaboration (Sirois et al., 2023) and the ManyBabies projects in infancy research. The multiverse approach here considers diverse traditions in processing of pupil size data in order to discuss whether and how the multiverse of statistical results promotes consensus knowledge beyond individual lab boundaries. Also, the talk aims at showing whether and how the multiverse approach to data analysis can give practical indications to organize interdisciplinary and collective expertise, to better define the constructs of interest and to improve their measurement. By navigating the uncertainty offered by infant eye-tracking data, the present contribution proposes the challenges and opportunities offered by the multiverse approach as a tool to get insights into the robustness of empirical evidence, to inform the dialogue between philosophy, psychology, and statistics, and boost the usefulness of collaborative efforts.

Title: Open Science Practice and Reproducibility in Preclinical Animal Research

Contributor(s): Monica Forni

Affiliations: Department of Medical and Surgical Sciences, Università di Bologna

Abstract:

The reproducibility crisis has manifested itself overwhelmingly in recent years in preclinical data obtained through animal experimentation as well as previously in research conducted in other fields. The lack of scientific value is an important reason to contest the use of animals and, in the profound conviction that animals are still fundamental to the advancement of knowledge in the biomedical field, it is absolutely necessary to take a step to the right direction. Since the creation of the first guidelines in the field (ARRIVE¹) based on the 3Rs (Replace, Reduce and Refine) the emphasis has been on transparency to enable society to have a correct perception of why and how experimentation is carried out. From here, the step towards open science is short! The correct planning of the study, and in particular a careful experimental design, certainly allows the application of the principles of the 3Rs in particular by 'reducing' the number of animals required to obtain results of proven scientific value. To improve the guidance on the specific knowledge and skills

required for designing, analyzing, and interpreting animal experiments FELASA (Federation of European Association of Laboratory Animals Science) has established a Working Group on Experimental design in education and training², with the aim of helping researchers undertaking projects to be in compliance with the requirements of the Directive EU2010/63. At a recent conference in Utrecht³, the relationship between open science and the reproducibility and transparency required in experiments using animals was made clear. In this context, it was pointed out that the most recent guidelines (PREPARE⁴) already contain a large number of elements related to open science. The writing of non-technical reports, which by law must be public and written in non-specific language understandable to the general public, and the need to make explicit the sources of research funding are indications in line with the principles of Open Science. The use of dedicated repositories for pre-registration of experiments is also increasingly being encouraged, and the proliferation of systematic reviews calls for more and more FAIR data repositories as an excellent reduction tool. The indications encouraging the exchange of samples and tissues, including through the creation of biobanks and databases, are a further element of Reduction on the one hand and pillars of open science on the other. The need to ALWAYS publish the results of animal experiments, including negative or unexpected results, in non-grey editorial placements is a fundamental principle to avoid unnecessary and unethical duplication and to provide researchers with the necessary baseline data to assess more accurately the sample size required for future studies. In conclusion, it is evident how open science can lead to better animal-based science by obtaining, from fewer animals, a greater mass of information of high scientific value.

¹ <https://arriveguidelines.org>

² <https://felasa.eu/working-groups/id/44>

³ <https://ivd-utrecht.nl/en/news/better-animal-research-through-open-science-1>

⁴ <https://norecopa.no/prepare>

Title: Il network NiCo (Network Italiano delle Core facilities)

Contributor(s): Valentina Adami

Affiliations: Università di Trento, Dipartimento CIBIO,

Abstract:

Le core facilities sono laboratori centralizzati all'interno di una rete o di un singolo ente di ricerca, con lo scopo di facilitare l'accesso dei ricercatori a strumentazioni all'avanguardia e tecnologie complesse difficilmente presenti nel singolo laboratorio avvalendosi dell'esperienza e la competenza di personale dedicato. Dato che la maggior parte dei dati generati nelle istituzioni di ricerca viene prodotta all'interno delle core facilities, queste rivestono un ruolo fondamentale nell'eccellenza scientifica. Il personale è infatti profondamente coinvolto in molti aspetti legati alla qualità e alla riproducibilità, applicando SOPs, aiutando i ricercatori a prevenire errori nel disegno sperimentale, utilizzando la massima trasparenza nel riportare i dettagli sperimentali e garantendo la qualità e l'autenticazione delle risorse utilizzate, nonché la corretta funzionalità degli strumenti. La Rete Italiana delle Core Facilities (NiCo) è nata nel 2022 dall'iniziativa di un gruppo di Atenei ed Enti di Ricerca che hanno avvertito l'esigenza di confrontarsi e di condividere esperienze di gestione di infrastrutture a supporto della ricerca nazionale nell'ambito delle scienze della vita. In particolare, NiCo è attualmente coinvolta nel progetto di rafforzamento

dell'infrastruttura BBMRI.it, con l'obiettivo di supportare il network italiano delle biobanche con servizi di alta qualità per la caratterizzazione dei campioni. Al momento la rete comprende undici istituzioni accademiche: Università di Trento, Università di Bologna, Università di Milano, Università di Milano Bicocca, Università di Pavia, Università di Pisa, Università di Verona, Università del Piemonte Orientale, Università di Chieti-Pescara, Istituto Superiore di Sanità e Stazione Zoologica Anton Dorn.